

Geometrically Exact Three-dimensional Modeling of Cable-Driven Parallel Manipulators for End-effector Positioning

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Abstract

A geometrically exact analytical model of cable-driven parallel manipulators operating in a three-dimensional space is formulated and discussed in this work. The model aims at investigating the exact positioning of a rigid body in a Cartesian space by a m -cables-driven parallel manipulator taking into account the cables mass, their elasticity and, consequently, the sag effect. The direct kinematic problem is formulated by means of $3(m + 1)$ nonlinear equations expressing compatibility and equilibrium in the same number of unknowns, namely, $3m$ components of the constraint reactions and 3 finite rotations. A novel approach to the solution of the inverse kinematic problem is formulated by adding a set of m target equations to obtain $4m + 3$ nonlinear algebraic equations solved in terms of an equal number of unknowns. The latter are defined by the $3(m + 1)$ increments of the variables of the direct problem and m additional unknowns, i.e., the increments of the cable unstretched lengths. The elastostatic problem of point mass end-effector is then derived. Consequently, the direct and the inverse kinematic problems are formulated by means of $3m$ and $4m$ nonlinear equations, respectively, in the equal number of unknowns. Examples with an increasing number of cables are considered, showing that, although solving the inverse kinematic problem may imply very slack cables configurations, the proposed approach allows to find a solution.

Keywords: cable-driven parallel manipulator, sagged cables, direct kinematics, inverse kinematics.

1. Introduction

Cable Driven Parallel Manipulators (CDPMs) have been introduced since few decades and are currently studied because of their inherent advantages with respect their classical counterparts composed by rigid links only. CDPMs belong to a class of parallel robots in which the fixed frame and the platform are connected by several cables, which can be exerted or retracted by suitable actuation systems. Main advantages refer to the very large workspace, relatively lightweight structure, reduction of the overall costs related to the main components of the system. In particular, the reduction of the moving masses leads to high acceleration capability of the end-effector; in addition, by changing the anchor points (i.e. the configuration for the actuation and pulleys) the robot can be easily reconfigured, being also modular.

These are important features for applications which requires a manipulator being brought to work on site. Several studies on cable-driven manipulators have been undertaken referring to their applications. Some works are related to the low inertia of such mechanisms for high-speed pick and place manipulators [1, 2, 3]. Applications taking advantage of the large workspace are the NIST Robocrane [4] and the systems proposed in [5, 6, 7]. Engineering challenges also include material handling over large areas, positioning for heavy

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15 objects, rescue operations, service, assistance, rehabilitation, entertainment [8] and even the Five hundred meter Aperture Spherical Telescope (FAST), as described in [9].

Drawbacks of CDPMs are related to the mechanical feature of cables, which can only work in tension. Therefore, the pose is feasible only for cables' configurations in which the static or dynamic equilibrium is assured under the constraint that the internal cable axial force must be positive. Although cable manipulators have been the subject of several research activities and started to be used for several applications, many of the fundamental problems regarding their kinematics, dynamics, and control are currently under study.

25 The main components of a CDPM are: the fixed frame (or structure), the end-effector, the cables, the actuation and the transmission system. Each of these elements should be correctly modeled in order to get a reliable mechanical design and realistic simulations of the cable system's behavior and then efficient control. In order to modify their length, cables are usually wound around a spool and the spool is rotated to release or retract the cable through suitable actuation system mounted on the same axis of the spool.

30 The anchor position is the point at which the cable leaves the spool. A correct modeling of the cables is crucial for the CDPM design. First mathematical models of CDPMs considered massless inextensible cables, being assumed as lines connecting the anchor points on the frame and end-effector [10]. Then axial flexibility was introduced for deriving the statics and the dynamics of the system. As clearly reported in the recent literature, cables cannot be modeled as inextensible, contrary to conventional limbs in parallel manipulators. This characteristic has led to model the stiffness of cable-actuated mechanisms; in [11] an equivalent stiffness model was proposed for a single cable, including the pretension, by using four springs. This feature of the cables also affects the reachable workspace and the available operational wrench of such manipulators, which turns out to be quite different from that of conventional parallel mechanism [12]. Lately, the current approach is to introduce the mass of the cables taking into account the transversal flexibility, either considering lumped masses [13] or continuum mass models. The first approach considers discretized cables by lumped mass method [14], finite element method [15], and finite segment method [16]. According to the lumped mass model, the mass of each cable element is lumped at specific point, nodes. The nodes of each element are considered to be connected by a spring and a damping element in parallel [8]. In the second approach cable model is considered a continuous and elastic medium, described by partial differential equation [17, 18]. In [19, 20, 21] the cable model was considered elastic and flexible, when elastic considers the object undergoing strain deformation, while flexible considers the object undergoing to bending deformation. Thermal effects were considered in [22].

45 The model adopted to describe the cable greatly influence the positioning capability addressed by Direct Kinematics (DK), and control of the system related to Inverse Kinematics (IK). First works on cable-driven robots dealt with DK considering massless and inextensible cable working only in tension under static or quasi-static conditions [23]. In this work, the model allowed to determine categories of robots which were classified by the controllability of the platform, in turn determined by the working cables m with respect to the number of degree-of-freedom n of the end-effector. In [7] the same model is used to determine wrench-feasible workspace (WFW), which is the set of all wrenches that a cable robot can apply to its surroundings without violating tension limits in the cables.

55 Subsequently, the effects of cable mass and elasticity on the accurate positioning of the end-effector have been considered by different authors [24, 25, 13]. The work of Kozak et al. has strongly influenced the subsequent literature because the equations describing the catenary configuration of the cable have been used considering the cable length as an unknown while the final position of the cable was assigned, leading therefore to an IK problem. Doing that the authors have solved a system of nonlinear equations in which $2m$ equations were provided by the catenary profiles in $3m$ unknowns ($2m$ cable reactions and m cable lengths). Therefore, in order to find a solution, n equilibrium equations have been added making the problem solvable in the case of minimally constrained system (only $m = n$). In [26] the authors solved DK for CDPMs by defining two Forward Kinematics (FK) problems: real time FK and full FK, respectively. In the first case, DK was used for control purposes with the objective of determining the current pose of the robot. In the second case, the aim was to determine all solutions of the FK finding all the possible initial equilibrium poses of the robot. The authors claimed that the problem for minimally constrained systems ($m = n = 6$) in a 3D Euclidian space can be solved by considering the equations describing the catenary ($2m$) and the

equilibrium equations (6) in terms of the $2m + 6$ unknowns given by the cable reaction forces and poses.

In the the equations describing the catenary the unknown can be the position of the cables' end (DK problem) or the cable lengths (IK problem). Indeed, for the DK problem (Forward Kinematics) treated in [26], the authors choose to represent the pose of the platform by the 12 coordinates in the reference frame of 4 of the points B_i , which are the not coplanar corners of the rigid body. Consequently, they added additional unknowns and additional equations ending up with $3m + 12$ unknowns for $3m + 12$ equations. Interval analysis was used to solve the full FK problem. In [27] both DK (full FK) and IK problems were considered; in the second case, the author assumed as unknowns $2m$ cable reaction forces and m cable lengths solved by $2m$ so-called Irvine constraint equations and 6 statics equations in the 3D Euclidean space. The minimally constrained systems ($m = n = 6$), overconstrained systems ($m > n = 6$) and underconstrained system ($m < n = 6$) were considered and, in all the investigated cases, the solution is searched by interval analysis.

In [24] the Inverse Kinematics (IK) problem is approached giving the end-effector pose and evaluating the cables reaction components and lengths, resulting in the plane $2m + m$ unknowns ($3m + m$ in space) having $2m$ catenary equations (Irvine, see [28]) and 3 (or 6) additional static equations being planar or spatial case. Therefore, depending on the number of cables, the obtained system of equations and unknowns can be determined, overdetermined or underdetermined. A numerical algorithm based on a combination of interval techniques and an iterative solver to estimate the pose for over-constrained cable robot (simply number of cables m is greater than the DOFs of the system n) was proposed in [29] neglecting sag effects. The over-constrained kinematic problem was solved searching for the minimization of a squared constrained error, which is related to potential energy stored in the cables. The IK problem is also analyzed in [30] with the hypothesis of inextensible cable first, and then using a parabolic cable profile equation. The problem was formulated again having as input the end-effector pose and evaluating the cable forces and lengths ($2m + m$ unknowns in the planar case).

Lately, the problem was approached by adopting continuation methods [31]. It is worth noting that for the reported literature, the balance between number of equations and unknowns depends by the number of cables. Nguyen et al. proposed in [32] a simplified model for Inverse Kinematics taking into account a sag cable. Criteria for stable convergence were discussed in [33]. In [34] an approach was proposed to solve the Direct Kinematics based on energy and optimization. Referring to the positioning capability, an interesting problem arises when CDPMs are in a crane configuration (also called suspended), gravity acts like an additional cable [4], and not all the end-effector DOFs can be controlled.

During the past few decades, this kind of robot has attracted an increasing interest among researchers. The first motivation for the study of crane type cable robots is because they offer several advantages. A suspended configuration may lead to a smaller number of cables that reduces the number of actuators, the overall costs and setup time, improved ease of assembly and a lower likelihood of cable interference. Referring to the kinematic study of suspended CDPRs, the challenging problem is that only less than 6 DOFs may be controlled, therefore, when the cable lengths are assigned, the end-effector still possesses some free degree of freedom. Thus, its actual pose is determined by the wrenches acting upon it [35] in which the problem has been defined as geometrico-static also expressing some connections between stability and energy [36]. Moreover, as the applied forces determine the pose of the end-effector, the latter may change due to external disturbances, therefore, it is necessary to study also the equilibrium stability.

In this paper, an analytical model is presented for solving the DK and the IK problems of CDPMs, working in a 3D space, based on a mixed formulation of a nonlinear elasto-static problem. In particular, it is shown that in the direct elasto-static problem the adopted formulation produces a number of unknowns always equal to the number of nonlinear equations. In particular, the adopted mixed formulation uses either static and kinematic unknowns as main variables, namely the reaction forces and the asset angles of the three-dimensional rigid body simulating the end-effector. The solution of the direct elasto-static problem contributes to solve the DK (or real time FK problem); indeed, within the proposed approach ones the cable unstretched lengths are assigned the end-effector pose is calculated, and both the equilibrium and the compatibility equations are satisfied, as preliminarily presented in [37]. Starting from this configuration the IK problem is solved in terms of the cables incremental unstretched lengths and tensions so that the exact assigned position of the end-effector is assured. To this end, a kinematic descriptor, namely the vectorial

distance between the end-effector position evaluated through a DK analysis and the target position, is minimized. It is also shown that there are specific regions in the 3D workspace where compatible and equilibrium solutions, providing the exact positioning of the end-effector, exist although entailing very slack configurations of at least one cable.

Thanks to the introduced compatibility equations, a further contribution of this work is that, in both IK and DK of minimally constrained and overconstrained cable systems, the solution can be pursued by solving a number of equations equal to the minimal number of unknowns, which are the component of the force reactions at the cables supports and the asset angles of the rigid body. Exact end-effector poses and stretched cable lengths are then evaluated in the IK problem.

2. Mechanical Formulation

A nonlinear parametric model of cable-driven parallel manipulators (CDPM) supporting an end-effector mass undergoing rigid rotations in a three-dimensional (3D) space is proposed to investigate the equilibrium configurations reached for assigned target positions and orientations of the end-effector. A general number of cables, having linear elastic constitutive behavior, is considered in the model and the overall mechanical description of the CDPM is provided in a 3D Euclidean space. Each of the m cables is fixed at one end and is connected to a different point on the end-effector mass; the number of degrees of freedom (DOFs) of the CDPM is indicated by n .

2.1. Kinematics

In Fig. 1 is illustrated a schematic representation of the CDPM equilibrium configurations which can be attained through direct (blue) and inverse (red) kinematic approach, respectively, starting from a target configuration (gray). The latter, corresponds also to the exact positioning achieved via inverse kinematic approach i.e., the red configuration. The proposed analytical model is parametrized in space by adopting the cables arclength $S_i \in [0, L_{0,i}]$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$) of the unstretched configuration, where $L_{0,i}$ is the total unstretched length of the i th cable. To describe the 3D kinematics of the CDPM, m fixed orthonormal frames $(\mathbf{e}_x^{(i)}, \mathbf{e}_y^{(i)}, \mathbf{e}_z^{(i)})$ with origin in the fixed boundary of the i th cable (i.e., the point O_i), and all collinear to each other, are introduced, where $\mathbf{e}_z^{(i)}$ represents the gravity direction with opposite sense [38], while $(\mathbf{e}_x^{(i)}, \mathbf{e}_y^{(i)})$ identifies the i th horizontal plane. To describe the cables configurations, the position vectors $\mathbf{p}_i(S_i) = x(S_i)\mathbf{e}_x^{(i)} + y(S_i)\mathbf{e}_y^{(i)} + z(S_i)\mathbf{e}_z^{(i)}$ are first introduced together with the unit vectors $\mathbf{a}_i = a_{i,x}\mathbf{e}_x^{(i)} + a_{i,y}\mathbf{e}_y^{(i)} + a_{i,z}\mathbf{e}_z^{(i)}$ tangent to the cables deformed arclength $s_i \in [0, L_i]$ (where L_i is the total deformed length of the i th cable), and whose components satisfy the condition $\|\mathbf{a}_i\| = \sqrt{a_{i,x}^2 + a_{i,y}^2 + a_{i,z}^2} = 1$. On the other hand, the orientation of the end-effector is given by the local frame $(\mathbf{b}_x^0, \mathbf{b}_y^0, \mathbf{b}_z^0)$ centered in the mass centroid and collinear to the m fixed frames $(\mathbf{e}_x^{(i)}, \mathbf{e}_y^{(i)}, \mathbf{e}_z^{(i)})$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$), see Fig. 1 (c). To determine the change of orientation of the mass M , the orthogonal tensor of the finite rotations undergone by the end-effector is introduced. Although the finite rotations of a Cartesian frame can be parametrized by different sequences of rotations (e.g., the proper Euler angles typically adopted in the study of rigid-body mechanics), however, in the present work, angles ϕ_x , ϕ_y , and ϕ_z were chosen so as to obtain the following rotation matrix \mathbf{R} :

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} c_y c_z & -c_y s_z & s_y \\ c_x s_z + s_x s_y c_z & c_x c_z - s_x s_y s_z & -s_x c_y \\ s_x s_z - c_x s_y c_z & s_x c_z + c_x s_y s_z & c_x c_y \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where s_j and c_j indicate $\sin \phi_j$ and $\cos \phi_j$, respectively, for $j = x, y, z$. In particular, the orthogonal matrix \mathbf{R} is obtained through the following sequence of finite rotations depicted in Fig. 1 (c): ϕ_x , about the axis collinear with $\mathbf{b}_x^0 \equiv \mathbf{e}_x^{(i)}$, ϕ_y , about the axis collinear with \mathbf{b}_y^* , and ϕ_z , about the axis collinear with \mathbf{b}_z .

The position of the support point of the i th cable, i.e., the point O_i , is provided in the fixed frame of the first cable by the vector $\mathbf{r}_{O_i} = b_{1i}\mathbf{e}_x^{(1)} + d_{1i}\mathbf{e}_y^{(1)} + h_{1i}\mathbf{e}_z^{(1)}$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$), where b_{1i} , d_{1i} and h_{1i} are the two horizontal and the vertical distances, respectively, between the fixed ends of the i th and the first cable. The

collocation in space of the i th connected point of the end-effector with respect to its center of mass is given through the vector $\mathbf{r}_{M,i}^0$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$) whose components in the local frame $(\mathbf{b}_x^0, \mathbf{b}_y^0, \mathbf{b}_z^0)$ depend on the selected geometry of the end-effector; although, due to the change of orientation of the mass with respect to the m fixed frames, the position vector of the i th connected point can be obtained as $\mathbf{r}_{M,i} = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{M,i}^0$, where $(.) \cdot (.)$ is the dot product. Finally, the vector providing the distance between the i th and the first connected point on the end-effector can be calculated as $\mathbf{r}_{i,1}^V = \mathbf{r}_{M,1} - \mathbf{r}_{M,i}$.

The cables configurations are found by considering target positions of the mass M and its orientation in space. To this end, the mass position is provided in the frame $(\mathbf{e}_x^{(1)}, \mathbf{e}_y^{(1)}, \mathbf{e}_z^{(1)})$ of the first cable by the vector \mathbf{p}_T , while the position of the end-effector point connected to the i th cable is provided by the vector $\mathbf{p}_{T,i} = l_i \tilde{\mathbf{a}}_i$, where l_i is the chord-wise distance between the cable fixed end and the i th end-effector point, and $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_i = \tilde{a}_{i,x} \mathbf{e}_x^{(i)} + \tilde{a}_{i,y} \mathbf{e}_y^{(i)} + \tilde{a}_{i,z} \mathbf{e}_z^{(i)}$ is the direction (i.e., $\|\tilde{\mathbf{a}}_i\| = 1$).

2.1.1. Target configurations in the 3D space

Once assigned the target position \mathbf{p}_T of the end-effector center of mass and the orientation of the mass, provided by the matrix \mathbf{R}_T , the target position vector of the first connected point of the end-effector can be straightforwardly calculated as

$$\mathbf{p}_{T,1} = \mathbf{p}_T + \mathbf{R}_T \cdot \mathbf{r}_{M,1}^0, \quad (2)$$

and the chord-wise distance l_1 can be calculated as the norm of $\mathbf{p}_{T,1}$, i.e.,

$$l_1 = \|\mathbf{p}_T + \mathbf{R}_T \cdot \mathbf{r}_{M,1}^0\|, \quad (3)$$

while the directors $\tilde{a}_{1,x}$, $\tilde{a}_{1,y}$, and $\tilde{a}_{1,z}$ can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{a}_{1,x} &= \frac{1}{l_1} (\mathbf{p}_T + \mathbf{R}_T \cdot \mathbf{r}_{M,1}^0) \cdot \mathbf{e}_x^{(1)}, \\ \tilde{a}_{1,y} &= \frac{1}{l_1} (\mathbf{p}_T + \mathbf{R}_T \cdot \mathbf{r}_{M,1}^0) \cdot \mathbf{e}_y^{(1)}, \\ \tilde{a}_{1,z} &= \frac{1}{l_1} (\mathbf{p}_T + \mathbf{R}_T \cdot \mathbf{r}_{M,1}^0) \cdot \mathbf{e}_z^{(1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Then, the expressions of the target position vectors $\mathbf{p}_{T,i}$ of the remaining $m - 1$ end-effector connected points with respect to the i th frame can be calculated by the following geometric compatibility relation: $\mathbf{p}_{T,i} = \mathbf{p}_{T,1} - \mathbf{r}_{i,1}^V - \mathbf{r}_{O_i}$. In particular, the latter can be written in component form as

$$\begin{aligned} l_i \tilde{a}_{i,x} &= l_1 \tilde{a}_{1,x} - \left(\mathbf{r}_{i,1}^V \cdot \mathbf{e}_x^{(i)} \right) - b_{1i}, \\ l_i \tilde{a}_{i,y} &= l_1 \tilde{a}_{1,y} - \left(\mathbf{r}_{i,1}^V \cdot \mathbf{e}_y^{(i)} \right) - d_{1i}, \\ l_i \tilde{a}_{i,z} &= l_1 \tilde{a}_{1,z} - \left(\mathbf{r}_{i,1}^V \cdot \mathbf{e}_z^{(i)} \right) - h_{1i}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

which, by introducing the $m - 1$ normalization conditions $\sqrt{\tilde{a}_{i,x}^2 + \tilde{a}_{i,y}^2 + \tilde{a}_{i,z}^2} = 1$, deliver the expressions of l_i , $\tilde{a}_{i,x}$, $\tilde{a}_{i,y}$, and $\tilde{a}_{i,z}$ ($i = 2, \dots, m$), respectively.

2.2. Equilibrium configurations of the elastic cables

In the continuum-based mechanical formulation proposed in this work, the cables flexibility [20, 21] is neglected, therefore, the strain parameter describing the deformation modes of the i th cable results only in the elongation ε_i , defined as $\varepsilon_i = ds_i/dS_i - 1$, where d stands for total differentiation. On the other hand, the tension in the i th cable is given by the vector $\mathbf{n}_i = N_i \mathbf{a}_i$, where N_i is expressed in terms of the cable elongation through the linear elastic constitutive relationship $N_i = E_i A_i \varepsilon_i$, being E_i and A_i the i th cable Young modulus and cross-sectional area, respectively.

The equilibrium equation of i th cable can be written in differential form as $d\mathbf{n}_i/dS_i - \rho A_i \mathbf{g} = \mathbf{o}$, where \mathbf{o} is the zero vector and ρA_i is the mass per unit length of the i th cable which is here assumed to be the

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the CDPM: (a) target configuration (gray) vs configuration calculated via DK (blue); (b) configuration calculated via DK (blue) and via IK (red). (c) Finite rotations and equilibrium of the forces acting on the end-effector mass.

same for each cable, i.e., $\rho A_i \equiv \rho A$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$). By now introducing the horizontal, T_i and H_i , and the vertical V_i components of the cable tension acting at the fixed end O_i of the i th cable (i.e., at $S_i = 0$, $N_i(0)a_{i,x}(0) = T_i$, $N_i(0)a_{i,y}(0) = H_i$, $N_i(0)a_{i,z}(0) = -V_i$), it is possible to deliver the integral form of the equilibrium of the i th cable as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_i a_{i,x} &= T_i, \\
 N_i a_{i,y} &= H_i, \\
 N_i a_{i,z} &= -V_i + \int_0^{S_i} \rho A g dS_i.
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

In Eq. (6), the integral term in the right-hand side of the third equation represents the weight of the i th cable having unstretched length S_i (i.e., $\rho A g S_i$) and g is the gravity acceleration. The solution

of Eq. (6) in terms of the components $a_{i,x}$, $a_{i,y}$ and $a_{i,z}$ of the unit vector \mathbf{a}_i , together with the normalization condition $\sqrt{a_{i,x}^2 + a_{i,y}^2 + a_{i,z}^2} = 1$, provides the expression of the tension in the i th cable as $N_i = \sqrt{H_i^2 + T_i^2 + (V_i - \rho A g S_i)^2}$.

By recalling the definition of the components of the unit vector \mathbf{a}_i , for which $a_{i,x} = dx_i/ds_i$, $a_{i,y} = dy_i/ds_i$ and $a_{i,z} = dz_i/ds_i$, respectively, and where $ds_i = (1 + \varepsilon_i)dS_i$, the latter, can be then combined with the inverse constitutive relation $\varepsilon_i = N_i/(E_i A_i)$ to calculate the equilibrium configuration of the i th cable in terms of the horizontal and the vertical components of the position vector $\mathbf{p}_i(S_i)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} x_i(S_i) &= \int_0^{S_i} \frac{T_i}{N_i} \left(\frac{N_i}{E_i A_i} + 1 \right) dS_i, \\ y_i(S_i) &= \int_0^{S_i} \frac{H_i}{N_i} \left(\frac{N_i}{E_i A_i} + 1 \right) dS_i, \\ z_i(S_i) &= \int_0^{S_i} \frac{(\rho A g S_i - V_i)}{N_i} \left(\frac{N_i}{E_i A_i} + 1 \right) dS_i, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where, from Eq. (6), $T_i/N_i = a_{i,x}$, $H_i/N_i = a_{i,y}$ and $(\rho A g S_i - V_i)/N_i = a_{i,z}$.

170 2.3. Nondimensional form

To cast the nonlinear equilibrium equations of the i th elastic cable in a suitable nondimensional form, the distance l_1 between the boundary points of the first cable is used as characteristic geometric parameter to rescale the mechanical problem. Thus, the nondimensional unstretched arclength of the i th cable becomes $\xi_i = S_i/l_1$, while $\bar{x}_i = x_i/l_1$, $\bar{y}_i = y_i/l_1$ and $\bar{z}_i = z_i/l_1$ are introduced to describe the nondimensional components of the position vector $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(S_i) = \mathbf{p}_i(S_i)/l_1$. Moreover, by introducing the reference force $f^c = \rho A g l_1$, the following nondimensional expression of the i th cable tension can be provided: $\bar{N}_i = \kappa_i \varepsilon_i$, where $\kappa_i = E_i A_i/f^c$ is the nondimensional cable stiffness. On the other hand, by defining $\alpha_i = T_i/f^c$, $\beta_i = H_i/f^c$, $\gamma_i = V_i/f^c$, \bar{N}_i can be alternatively expressed as $\bar{N}_i = \sqrt{\xi_i^2 + \alpha_i^2 + \beta_i^2 + \gamma_i^2 - 2\xi_i \gamma_i}$. Finally, by including the fixed boundary conditions at the cables supports, i.e., $\bar{x}_i(0) = \bar{y}_i(0) = \bar{z}_i(0) = 0$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$), the solution of Eq. (7), in its nondimensional form, can be written as [28]:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{x}_i(\xi_i) &= \bar{x}_i(0) + \alpha_i \left[\frac{\xi_i}{\kappa_i} + \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{\xi_i - \gamma_i}{\sqrt{\alpha_i^2 + \beta_i^2}} \right) + \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{\gamma_i}{\sqrt{\alpha_i^2 + \beta_i^2}} \right) \right], \\ \bar{y}_i(\xi_i) &= \bar{y}_i(0) + \beta_i \left[\frac{\xi_i}{\kappa_i} + \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{\xi_i - \gamma_i}{\sqrt{\alpha_i^2 + \beta_i^2}} \right) + \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{\gamma_i}{\sqrt{\alpha_i^2 + \beta_i^2}} \right) \right], \\ \bar{z}_i(\xi_i) &= \bar{z}_i(0) + \frac{\xi_i(\xi_i - 2\gamma_i)}{2\kappa_i} + \sqrt{\xi_i^2 + \alpha_i^2 + \beta_i^2 + \gamma_i^2 - 2\xi_i \gamma_i} - \sqrt{\alpha_i^2 + \beta_i^2 + \gamma_i^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where \sinh^{-1} is the inverse hyperbolic sine function.

3. Equilibrium and kinematic compatibility of the CDPM

The equations system (8), which holds for all the m cables (i.e., $i = 1, \dots, m$), provides the equilibrium configuration of the i th cable as a function of its elastic stiffness κ_i and of the nondimensional forces α_i , β_i and γ_i at the cable fixed boundary. On the other hand, the equilibrium of the whole mechanical system made by the m cables and the end-effector mass is assured by providing that the resultant force in the system must be zero and that the resultant moment of the forces about any point must be zero. These two conditions are satisfied when

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_i = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i - \sum_{i=1}^m \eta_i - \bar{W} = 0, \quad (9)$$

and, considering the end-effector center of mass as point for calculating the moment of the forces (see Fig. 1 (c)), when

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{M,i} \times \bar{\mathbf{n}}_i(\eta_i) = \mathbf{o}, \quad (10)$$

respectively, where $(.) \times (.)$ is the cross product. In Eq. (9), $\bar{W} = M g / f^c$ is the nondimensional weight of the end-effector, while $\eta_i = \rho A g L_{0,i} / f^c$ represents the nondimensional total weight of the i th cable, which, in turn, corresponds to the ratio between the unstretched length $L_{0,i}$ of the i th cable and the span l_1 of the first cable, i.e., $\eta_i = L_{0,i} / l_1$. Finally, in Eq. (10), $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{M,i} = \mathbf{r}_{M,i} / l_1$ and $\bar{\mathbf{n}}_i(\eta_i) = \alpha_i \mathbf{e}_x^{(i)} + \beta_i \mathbf{e}_y^{(i)} + (\gamma_i - \eta_i) \mathbf{e}_z^{(i)}$ is the vector of the cable nondimensional axial force acting at the i th end-effector connected point (i.e., for $\xi_i = \eta_i$).

To assure that the free ends of the m cables are connected to different points of the end-effector mass, kinematic compatibility conditions must be then provided. To this end, the following $m-1$ vectorial relations hold

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{O_i} + \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i) + \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{i,1}^V - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_1(\eta_1) = \mathbf{o}, \quad (i = 2, \dots, m), \quad (11)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{O_i} = \mathbf{r}_{O_i} / l_1$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{i,1}^V = \mathbf{r}_{i,1}^V / l_1$, while $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_1(\eta_1)$ and $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i)$ are the nondimensional position vectors of the first and the i th connection point on the end-effector, respectively (i.e., when $\xi_1 = \eta_1$ and $\xi_i = \eta_i$).

3.1. Direct approach to the kinematic problem

The component form of Eq. (11) provides $3(m-1)$ scalar equations representing the kinematic compatibility conditions of the mechanical system, while the equilibrium of the system is provided by the 3 equations in Eq. (9) and the 3 scalar components of Eq. (10). The unknowns of the mechanical problem here formulated are a total of $3(m+1)$, namely, the $3m$ components of the cables tension at the fixed boundaries α_i , β_i and γ_i ($i = 1, \dots, m$), respectively, and the three rotations ϕ_x , ϕ_y and ϕ_z undergone by the end-effector mass. The solution of the obtained system of $3(m+1)$ nonlinear equations in $3(m+1)$ unknowns can be sought numerically by adopting a direct kinematic (DK) approach.

To this end, the target position and orientation of the end-effector mass are assigned by means of the vector $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_T = \mathbf{p}_T / l_1$ and the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_T = \mathbf{R}_T(\phi_{T,x}, \phi_{T,y}, \phi_{T,z})$, respectively. Due to the elastic features of the cables, the DK formulation does not assure that the target configuration of the CDPM can be reached for assigned (i.e., selected *a priori*) lengths $L_{0,i}$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$) of the cables unstretched configurations (i.e., the nondimensional parameters η_i).

Due to the complexity of finding closed-form solutions of such strongly nonlinear mechanical problem, approximate solutions of the $3(m+1)$ nonlinear equations can be found numerically by using minimization methods. In this work, the Random Search Algorithm [39], implemented in the software Mathematica [40] was adopted to find numerical approximations of the solution of Eqs. (9-11). The algorithm works by generating a population of random starting points, here chosen to be 500, and adopts a local optimization method for each of the starting points in order to converge to a local minimum of the objective function here taken as the norm of the $(3(m+1) \times 1)$ vector collecting the left-hand side (*LHS*) of the system made by the $3(m+1)$ nonlinear equilibrium and compatibility equations, i.e., Eqs. (9-11). The best local minimum of $\|LHS\|$ is then chosen to be the solution of the problem. Moreover, to exclude possible periodic solutions of the of rotations unknowns, the constraints $0 \leq \phi_x < 2\pi$, $0 \leq \phi_y < 2\pi$, and $0 \leq \phi_z < 2\pi$, are further provided in the algorithm. Unfortunately, as already mentioned, a strong limitation of the direct approach derives from the cables elasticity, which implies that the final position and orientation of the mass will not correspond to the desired configuration, that is, $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i) \neq \bar{\mathbf{p}}_{T,i}$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$).

3.2. Inverse approach to the kinematic problem

The inverse kinematic (IK) approach is used to drive the end-effector to the target collocation in space. More specifically, a solution is found starting from a given pose calculated in the DK problem. To this end, the m vectors $\Delta \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i) = \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i) - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_{T,i}$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$), each of which represents the difference vector between the position vector of the i th end-effector connected point and the target position vector of the same point, both given in the fixed frame of the i th cable, are introduced next. It is a matter of fact that, due to the cables elasticity, the missing correspondence between the target position and orientation of the end-effector and the solution calculated via a direct kinematic approach will lead to $\Delta \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i) \neq \mathbf{o}$.

The innovative approach pursued in this paper to overcome the limitation of the DK problem proposes a solution strategy based on the formulation of an incremental IK problem. Starting from the configuration calculated through the direct approach, for a selected target collocation of the end-effector (i.e., the position

of the center of mass and its orientation), the equilibrium equations (9)-(10) and the compatibility equations (11) are first rewritten in terms of incremental variables. To this end, the expressions $\alpha_i = \alpha_i^D + \Delta\alpha_i$, $\beta_i = \beta_i^D + \Delta\beta_i$, $\gamma_i = \gamma_i^D + \Delta\gamma_i$ and $\eta_i = \eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i$, are introduced, where α^D , β_i^D and γ_i^D are the solution of the direct problem, while η_i^0 is the *a priori* assigned parameter providing the unstretched length of the i th cable. It is worth noting that, differently from the DK problem, in the IK approach the cables unstretched length (in terms of its increment, i.e., $\Delta\eta_i$) becomes now a further unknowns of the problem. Therefore, the IK approach here formulated, allows to find the initial, unstretched, length $L_{0,i}^1$ to assign to each of the m elastic cables so as to reach the exact positioning of the end-effector, i.e., $L_{0,i}^1 = (\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i)l_1$. Furthermore, the incremental rotations $\Delta\phi_x$, $\Delta\phi_y$ and $\Delta\phi_z$ are considered so as to introduce the total rotations $\phi_x = \phi_x^D + \Delta\phi_x$, $\phi_y = \phi_y^D + \Delta\phi_y$, $\phi_z = \phi_z^D + \Delta\phi_z$, where ϕ_x^D , ϕ_y^D and ϕ_z^D are the rotations evaluated through the direct approach.

According to the definitions introduced above to describe the incremental problem, the exact (target) position and orientation of the end-effector mass are obtained when, in addition to the equilibrium and the compatibility equations, the following m vectorial equations hold (i.e., $i = 1, \dots, m$):

$$\Delta\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) = \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_{T,i} = \mathbf{o}, \quad (12)$$

which is verified when $\|\Delta\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i)\| = 0$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$). The latter, represents the i th of m additional scalar equations, here introduced and named as *target equations*, that must be satisfied together with the $3(m+1)$ nonlinear equations (9)-(10)-(11), respectively, written in terms of incremental variables. Therefore, the resulting system of $4m + 3$ equations

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^m (\alpha_i^D + \Delta\alpha_i) &= 0, \\ \sum_{i=1}^m (\beta_i^D + \Delta\beta_i) &= 0, \\ \sum_{i=1}^m (\gamma_i^D + \Delta\gamma_i) - \sum_{i=1}^m (\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) - \bar{W} &= 0, \\ \sum_{i=1}^m \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{M,i}(\phi_j^D + \Delta\phi_j) \times \bar{\mathbf{n}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) &= \mathbf{o}, \\ \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{O_i} + \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) + \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{i,1}^V(\phi_j^D + \Delta\phi_j) - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_1(\eta_1^0 + \Delta\eta_1) &= \mathbf{o}, \quad (i = 2, \dots, m), \\ \|\Delta\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i)\| &= 0, \quad (i = 1, \dots, m), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

can be solved numerically in terms of the $4m + 3$ incremental unknowns: $\Delta\alpha_i$, $\Delta\beta_i$, $\Delta\gamma_i$, $\Delta\eta_i$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$), and $\Delta\phi_x$, $\Delta\phi_y$, $\Delta\phi_z$, respectively. Note that, in Eq. (13), the subscript j stands for $j = x, y, z$.

In accordance with the numerical procedure adopted in the DK approach to solve the nonlinear problem of dimension $3(m+1)$, the numerical global optimization based on the Random Search algorithm is adopted to minimize the objective function given, for the case of the inverse kinematics, by the norm $\|LHS\|$, which is, in this case, the norm of the $((4m+3) \times 1)$ vector collecting the left-hand side of the nonlinear equations system (13). It is worth noting again that the problem formulation allows to obtain a system having the same number of equations and unknowns, being independent by the number of the system DOFs.

4. The case of point mass end-effector

The case of point mass end-effector can be straightforwardly derived from the full model presented in the previous sections by noting that, in this case, the end-effector does not possess an orientation in space since its geometry ideally reduces to a point (see the schematic representation in Fig. 2). Therefore, the rotations of the local frame $(\mathbf{b}_x^0, \mathbf{b}_y^0, \mathbf{b}_z^0)$ can be set equal to zero, i.e., $\phi_j^D = 0 = \Delta\phi_j$ ($j = x, y, z$). Moreover, since the end-effector is modeled as a point, then $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{M,i}(\phi_j^D) = \mathbf{o} = \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{M,i}(\phi_j^D + \Delta\phi_j)$, which implies

that $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{i,1}^V(\phi_j^D) = \mathbf{o} = \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{i,1}^V(\phi_j^D + \Delta\phi_j)$. Furthermore, the equilibrium of the system is satisfied only by means of Eq. (9), hence Eq. (10) can be neglected. Finally, the compatibility condition (11) reduces to $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{O_i} + \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i) - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_1(\eta_1) = \mathbf{o}$, ($i = 2, \dots, m$).

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the CDPM for the case of point mass end-effector.

The direct problem can be then formulated in terms of the $3m$ unknowns α_i , β_i , and γ_i , satisfying the following $3m$ equations

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_i = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i - \sum_{i=1}^m \eta_i - \bar{W} = 0, \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{O_i} + \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i) - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_1(\eta_1) = \mathbf{o}, \quad (i = 2, \dots, m).$$

On the other hand, the incremental form of the inverse problem, in the case of point mass, can be formulated in terms of the $4m$ unknowns $\Delta\alpha_i$, $\Delta\beta_i$, $\Delta\gamma_i$, and $\Delta\eta_i$ satisfying the following $4m$ equations

$$\sum_{i=1}^m (\alpha_i^D + \Delta\alpha_i) = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^m (\beta_i^D + \Delta\beta_i) = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^m (\gamma_i^D + \Delta\gamma_i) - \sum_{i=1}^m (\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) - \bar{W} = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{O_i} + \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_1(\eta_1^0 + \Delta\eta_1) = \mathbf{o}, \quad (i = 2, \dots, m),$$

$$\|\Delta\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i)\| = 0, \quad (i = 1, \dots, m),$$

where

$$\Delta\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) = \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{O_i} + \bar{\mathbf{p}}_i(\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i) - \bar{\mathbf{p}}_T. \quad (16)$$

Note that, Eq. (16) corresponds to Eq. (12) since the target position vector $\mathbf{p}_{T,i}$ reduces to $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{T,i} = \bar{\mathbf{p}}_T - \bar{\mathbf{r}}_{O_i}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_{T,1} \equiv \bar{\mathbf{p}}_T$ for $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{i,1}^V = \mathbf{o}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{M,i} = \mathbf{o}$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$).

5. Geometric and mechanical parameters of the selected CDPMs

Hereafter, the mechanical parameters reported in [41, 37] are adopted for the simulations performed in this work. In particular, all cables are characterized by the same axial stiffness $E_i A_i = 6.283 \times 10^2$ N ($i = 1, \dots, m$) and mass per unit length $\rho A = 1.12 \times 10^{-3}$ kg/m, while the end-effector mass is $M =$

53.26 $\times 10^{-3}$ kg. Moreover, although the geometry of the 3D end-effector mass here modeled can be general, in the present work was considered a square cuboid having height of 0.1 m and the two square faces having edges length of 0.05 m. Therefore, the collocation in space of the eight points of the 3D end-effector with respect to its center of mass is given by the following dimensional vectors (dimensions are in meters):
 $\mathbf{r}_{M,1}^0 = -0.05\mathbf{b}_x^0 - 0.025\mathbf{b}_y^0 + 0.025\mathbf{b}_z^0$, $\mathbf{r}_{M,2}^0 = -0.05\mathbf{b}_x^0 + 0.025\mathbf{b}_y^0 + 0.025\mathbf{b}_z^0$, $\mathbf{r}_{M,3}^0 = 0.05\mathbf{b}_x^0 + 0.025\mathbf{b}_y^0 + 0.025\mathbf{b}_z^0$,
 $\mathbf{r}_{M,4}^0 = 0.05\mathbf{b}_x^0 - 0.025\mathbf{b}_y^0 + 0.025\mathbf{b}_z^0$, $\mathbf{r}_{M,5}^0 = -0.05\mathbf{b}_x^0 - 0.025\mathbf{b}_y^0 - 0.025\mathbf{b}_z^0$, $\mathbf{r}_{M,6}^0 = -0.05\mathbf{b}_x^0 + 0.025\mathbf{b}_y^0 - 0.025\mathbf{b}_z^0$,
 $\mathbf{r}_{M,7}^0 = 0.05\mathbf{b}_x^0 + 0.025\mathbf{b}_y^0 - 0.025\mathbf{b}_z^0$, $\mathbf{r}_{M,8}^0 = 0.05\mathbf{b}_x^0 - 0.025\mathbf{b}_y^0 - 0.025\mathbf{b}_z^0$.

First, the case of 3D end-effector mass is studied for one assigned target position and orientation in space and by considering the case of eight, six and four suspension cables, respectively. The three case-studies are indicated as Case 1, Case 2, and Case 3, respectively, and the coordinates of the cables fixed points for the three cases are reported in Tab. 1. Then, studies on the problem of point mass end-effector are provided for five case-studies for which the positions of the cables fixed ends are reported in Tab. 2.

Table 1: Distances (in [m]) of the cables fixed ends from the origin of the first reference frame for the three case-studies configurations of the CDPM with 3D mass end-effector.

ith cable		2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Case 1	b_{1i}	0	1.5	1.5	0	0	1.5	1.5
	d_{1i}	1.5	1.5	0	0	1.5	1.5	0
	h_{1i}	0	0	0	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5
Case 2	b_{1i}	0	1.5	1.5	-	-	1.5	1.5
	d_{1i}	1.5	1.5	0	-	-	1.5	0
	h_{1i}	0	0	0	-	-	-0.5	-0.5
Case 3	d_{1i}	0	1.5	1.5	-	-	-	-
	b_{1i}	1.5	1.5	0	-	-	-	-
	h_{1i}	0	0	0	-	-	-	-

Table 2: Distances (in [m]) of the cables fixed ends from the origin of the first reference frame for the five case-studies configurations of the CDPM with point mass end-effector.

ith cable		2	3	4	5	6
Case 1	b_{1i}	1.673	0.448	-	-	-
	d_{1i}	0.448	1.673	-	-	-
	h_{1i}	0	0	-	-	-
Case 2	b_{1i}	1.414	1.414	0	-	-
	d_{1i}	0	1.414	1.414	-	-
	h_{1i}	0	0	0	-	-
Case 3	b_{1i}	1.161	1.695	0.863	-0.184	-
	d_{1i}	-0.184	0.863	1.695	1.161	-
	h_{1i}	0	0	0	0	-
Case 4	b_{1i}	1.414	1.414	0	-	-
	d_{1i}	0	1.414	1.414	-	-
	h_{1i}	0.5	0.25	-0.5	-	-
Case 5	b_{1i}	0.966	1.673	1.414	0.448	-0.259
	d_{1i}	-0.259	0.448	1.414	1.673	0.966
	h_{1i}	0	0	0	0	0

For all case-studies analyzed, the *a priori* assigned unstretched length of the i th cable, i.e., the tentative

265 unstretched length, is provided by assigning the cable aspect ratio Λ_i^0 [42, 28, 22], that is, the ratio between
the unstretched cable length $L_{0,i}$ and the distance l_i between its fixed end and the i th end-effector point
(i.e., $\Lambda_i^0 = L_{0,i}/l_i$). Consequently, the tentative nondimensional unstretched length of the i th cable can be
calculated as $\eta_i^0 = \Lambda_i^0 l_i/l_1$. As reported in [41], the sensitivity of the end-effector mass positioning with
270 respect to the prescribed parameter Λ_i^0 is a study of valuable interest in the case of direct kinematic approach,
where the accurate tuning of Λ_i^0 may provide an end-effector mass positioning close, although not coincident,
to the target position. On the other hand, the solution of the inverse kinematic approach here presented,
where the incremental unstretched length is a further unknown of the problem (i.e., its nondimensional
counterpart $\Delta\eta_i$), delivers the effective aspect ratio Λ_i of the i th cable to assign so as to reach the desired
position and orientation of the end-effector, i.e., $\Lambda_i = (\eta_i^0 + \Delta\eta_i)l_1/l_i$. It is worth mentioning that, the
275 tentative aspect ratio Λ_i^0 and the effective aspect ratio Λ_i have a purely geometric meaning and can be
adopted as parameters to estimate the pre-tension state of the i th cable. In particular, when $\Lambda_i \leq 1$ it turns
out that the i th cable has to be pre-tensioned in order to correctly put in position the end-effector; on the
other hand, when $\Lambda_i \gg 1$, the i th cable possesses a very loose initial configuration, therefore, it is not
suitable for practical applications.

280 In all the case-studies here investigated the tentative value of the cables aspect ratio Λ_i^0 is set equal to
1.01 for each cable (i.e., $i = 1, \dots, m$), while the values of the effective aspect ratio Λ_i , provided by the
solution of the IK problem, are calculated for all case-studies.

6. Application of the proposed model for DK and IK problems

In this Section, different configurations of spatial CDPMs were considered in order to show the capability
285 of the proposed modeling and methodology to solve DK and IK problems. First, the model is adopted to
investigate the case of 3D end-effector and to study the cables configurations leading to the exact positioning
and orientation of the mass by considering only taut or moderately slack cables configurations (i.e., $\Lambda_i \leq 1.1$).
Then, for the case of point mass CDPMs, workspaces excluding cables configurations having $\Lambda_i > 1.1$ (i.e.,
slack cables) are mapped for increasing number of suspension cables. Finally, the versatility of the here
290 proposed modeling is shown by means of an example in which a defined helicoidal trajectory in the workspace
is followed for a given number of suspension cables.

6.1. CDPM with 3D end-effector

Considering a spatial CDPM with $n = 6$ degrees of freedom of the end-effector and the m number of
cables, three relevant cases have been studied as an example belonging to each of the following classes:
295 overconstrained systems ($m > n$), minimally constrained systems ($m = n$), and underconstrained systems
($m < n$), respectively.

Fig. 3 shows the case of overconstrained CDPM with $m = 8$ cables whose fixed ends coordinates are given
in Tab. 1. In particular, in Fig. 3a the dashed lines represent the chords between the cables fixed boundaries
and the end-effector connected points (gray lines) and the end-effector (black lines) in the CDPM target
300 configuration, while the blue lines show the cables configurations and the end-effector orientation attained
through the DK approach. The minimization procedure of the LHS in the DK problem led to residual of
the norm equal to $\|LHS\| = 4.3 \times 10^{-6}$, corresponding to an average value $\overline{LHS} = 9.8 \times 10^{-8}$. Nevertheless,
for assigned cables lengths Λ_i^0 the DK approach cannot ensure the exact collocation of the end-effector, and
the error in predicting the target configuration is shown in Tab. 3 in terms of the percentage differences
305 between the calculated x , y , and z coordinates of the end-effector connected points with respect to the
target coordinates. On the other hand, the addition of m the target equations deriving from Eq. (12)
allows, in the IK, to calculate suitable unstretched cables lengths so as to match the target collocation in
space of the 3D end-effector as depicted in Fig. 3b, where is shown the comparison between the DK (blue
lines) and IK (red lines) solutions for the assigned target configuration. The high accuracy of the solution
310 calculated via the IK approach including the target equations, can be appreciated in Fig. 3c where is shown
the detail of end-effector position and orientation reached by the DK (blue) and IK (red) approaches, and
the configuration assigned as target (black, dashed). The accuracy in positioning the end-effector, i.e., the

error with respect to the target position, is less than the numerical tolerances of the solver. As a result of the overconstrained CDPM example, it is worth noting that the solution of the IK problem includes necessarily the presence of $m - n = 2$ slack cables in order to satisfy the equilibrium and the kinematic compatibility of the mechanical system. In particular, cables $i = 5, 6$ result in a moderately slack configuration corresponding to a $1 < \Lambda_i \leq 1.1$, while the resulting 6 cables are taut (i.e., $\Lambda_i \leq 1$), as shown in the last column of Tab. 3 where are reported the effective aspect ratios of the m cables in the solution of the IK problem. The latter, is obtained with a residual of the norm equal to $\|LHS\| = 1.8 \times 10^{-5}$, corresponding to an average value $\overline{LHS} = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$.

Figure 3: Eight cables equilibrium configurations ($\Lambda_i^0 = 1.01$) for 3D mass end-effector: DK (blue lines) vs. IK (red lines) approach (dimensions are in [m]).

The effective redundancy of two of the eight cables of the above discussed case-study (Case 1), is confirmed by the results of Case 2 shown in Fig. 4, where six cables, corresponding to the case of minimally constrained system ($m = n$), were adopted to find the target configuration of the CDPM. In particular, Case 2 is obtained by removing the two slack cables of Case 1 and the cables fixed ends coordinates are given in Tab. 1. Fig. 4a shows the configuration obtained in the DK approach, while Fig. 4b highlights the differences in the solution of the IK problems with respect to the DK case. The same accuracy of the solution calculated via the IK approach obtained in Case 1 can be appreciated also in the six cables case, as shown in Fig. 4c where the DK (blue), IK (red), and the target (black, dashed) configuration are emphasized in the close-up view. In Tab. 4, is reported the solution calculated via DK approach in terms of the x , y , and z components of the position vectors of the six connected points on the end-effector, together with the target

Table 3: Eight cables CDPM (Case 1), coordinates of the cables attachment points on the 3D mass end-effector, target coordinates x_T , y_T , and z_T vs results of the DK approach x_D, y_D , and z_D , and their percentage difference. The last column shows the cables effective aspect ratio in the IK approach.

i th cable	x_T [m]	y_T [m]	z_T [m]	x_D [m]	y_D [m]	z_D [m]	Δx_D [%]	Δy_D [%]	Δz_D [%]	Λ_i
1	1.149	0.943	-0.364	1.158	0.947	-0.387	0.8	0.4	6.3	0.999
2	1.146	0.991	-0.352	1.152	0.997	-0.394	0.5	0.6	11.9	0.999
3	1.244	0.995	-0.338	1.212	0.993	-0.474	-2.6	-0.2	40.2	0.999
4	1.248	0.947	-0.35	1.218	0.943	-0.467	-2.4	-0.4	33.4	0.999
5	1.156	0.955	-0.412	1.118	0.939	-0.417	-3.3	-1.7	1.2	1.192
6	1.152	1.003	-0.4	1.112	0.988	-0.423	-3.5	-1.5	5.7	1.245
7	1.251	1.007	-0.386	1.172	0.984	-0.503	-6.3	-2.3	30.3	0.999
8	1.254	0.959	-0.398	1.178	0.935	-0.497	-6.1	-2.5	24.9	1.0

coordinates and the corresponding percentage differences. The minimization procedure of the LHS in the DK problem led to residual of the norm equal to $\|LHS\| = 5.1 \times 10^{-6}$, corresponding to an average value $\overline{LHS} = -6.4 \times 10^{-8}$, while the solution of IK problem is achieved with an error such that $\|LHS\| = 1.1 \times 10^{-5}$ and $\overline{LHS} = 5.7 \times 10^{-7}$, respectively. Finally, the last column of Tab. 4 provides the values of the effective aspect ratio Λ_i of each cable calculated via the IK approach, showing the perfect correspondence with the values of the six taut cables of Case 1 (i.e., $i = 1, \dots, 4$ and $i = 7, 8$).

Table 4: Six cables CDPM (Case 2), coordinates of the cables attachment points on the 3D mass end-effector, target coordinates x_T , y_T , and z_T vs results of the DK approach x_D, y_D , and z_D , and their percentage difference. The last column shows the cables effective aspect ratio in the IK approach.

i th cable	x_T [m]	y_T [m]	z_T [m]	x_D [m]	y_D [m]	z_D [m]	Δx_D [%]	Δy_D [%]	Δz_D [%]	Λ_i
1	1.149	0.943	-0.364	1.158	0.947	-0.387	0.8	0.4	6.3	0.999
2	1.146	0.991	-0.352	1.15	0.995	-0.399	0.3	0.4	13.4	0.999
3	1.244	0.995	-0.338	1.22	0.989	-0.471	-1.9	-0.6	39.3	0.999
4	1.248	0.947	-0.35	1.228	0.941	-0.459	-1.6	-0.6	31.1	0.999
7	1.251	1.007	-0.386	1.185	0.976	-0.503	-5.3	-3.1	30.3	0.999
8	1.254	0.959	-0.398	1.192	0.928	-0.492	-4.9	-3.2	23.6	1.0

The last case-study proposed, is the example of an underconstrained CDPM (i.e., Case 3), here obtained by further removing cables $i = 7, 8$ from Case 2. In particular, the four cables considered in the case-study are connected at the top face of the end-effector cuboid mass, causing the inability of the elastic suspension system to provide the exact orientation in space of the end-effector. The blue lines in Fig. 5a depicts the configuration obtained by solving the DK problem, while Fig. 5b shows the comparison between the solution of the DK (blue lines) and the IK (red lines) problems. It is worth noting that, even in the case of underconstrained CDPM (i.e., $m < n$), a valid solution of the DK problem always exists, i.e., a small error in the norm of LHS and of its average value \overline{LHS} (in the case-study investigated equal to $\|LHS\| = 1.6 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\overline{LHS} = -5.5 \times 10^{-8}$, respectively) is found, although, the DK approach still does not allow to reach a target configuration due to the cables elongation. On the other hand, when $m < n$ in the IK problem it is not possible to find a solution verifying both the equilibrium and the kinematic compatibility of the system. As expected, although the here proposed approach makes use of additional m target equations (i.e., the norm of Eq. (12)) to force the solution to an assigned configuration, the procedure is still unable to find a minimum of the norm of LHS (i.e., $\|LHS\| = 2.1 \times 10^{-2}$ and $\overline{LHS} = 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$). The direct consequence of the non convergence of the minimization procedure in the underconstrained case is shown in Fig. 5c where in the solution of the IK problem (red) the kinematic compatibility of the end-effector connection points is

Figure 4: Six cables equilibrium configurations ($\Lambda_i^0 = 1.01$) for 3D mass end-effector: DK (blue lines) vs. IK (red lines) approach (dimensions are in [m]).

not respected. Furthermore, in Tab. 5 can be appreciated the errors of the solution of the IK problem in terms of the components of the position vectors of the end-effector connected points, although taut cables configurations are obtained for all cables, i.e., $\Lambda_i \leq 1$.

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Table 5: Four cables CDPM (Case 3), coordinates of the cables attachment points on the 3D mass end-effector, target coordinates x_T , y_T , and z_T vs results of the IK approach x_I, y_I , and z_I , and their percentage difference. The last column shows the cables effective aspect ratio in the IK approach.

i th cable	x_T [m]	y_T [m]	z_T [m]	x_I [m]	y_I [m]	z_I [m]	Δx_I [%]	Δy_I [%]	Δz_I [%]	Λ_i
1	0.925	0.948	-0.477	0.929	0.947	-0.458	0.43	-0.11	-3.98	0.996
2	0.924	0.998	-0.476	0.922	0.994	-0.378	-0.22	-0.4	0.42	0.995
3	1.024	1.0	-0.473	1.02	0.999	-0.485	-0.39	-0.1	2.54	0.974
4	1.025	0.95	-0.475	1.026	0.954	-0.476	0.1	0.42	0.21	0.988

6.2. Workspace of point mass CDPMs

For the case of point mass CDPM in a 3D space where $n = 3$, a deep investigation of the cables configurations was performed so as to define the workspace where all cables are taut (i.e., $\Lambda_i \leq 1$) or

Figure 5: Four cables equilibrium configurations ($\Lambda_i^0 = 1.01$) for 3D mass end-effector: DK (blue lines) vs. IK (red lines) approach (dimensions are in [m]).

moderately slack (i.e., $1 < \Lambda_i \leq 1.1$) without redundant slack cables. For all case-studies m is assumed so as to not consider underconstrained circumstances, therefore $m \geq n$; furthermore, a thick, uniform grid of ≈ 3500 target points was used to determine, via the inverse kinematic approach, the point mass end-effector configurations showing no cables redundancy. In Figs. 6a-b, 7a-b, and 8a-b are shown, for the cases of three, four, and five cables, respectively, in grey, the target points for which at least one cable results slack (i.e., $\Lambda_i > 1.1$), therefore redundant, while, in blue, are shown the target positions reached by taut or moderately slack cables configurations (i.e., $\Lambda_i \leq 1.1$). On the other hand, Figs. 6c-d, 7c-d, and 8c-d show the cables configurations for selected target points in the workspace reached via direct (blue lines) and inverse (red lines) kinematic approaches, respectively. In particular, in Figs. 6c, 7c, 8c, are depicted CDPM configurations for the cases of end-effector mass collocated inside the workspace, consequently, all cables result taut (or moderately slack) and the configurations found via IK approach (red lines) provide the exact positioning of the end-effector (i.e., the error with respect to the target position, is less than the numerical tolerances of the solver). On the other hand, Figs. 6d, 7d, and 8d, show CDPM configurations for the cases of end-effector mass collocated outside the workspace; those are the cases when the solution of the IK problem provides at least one very slack cable (i.e., $\Lambda_i > 1.1$). The values of Λ_i of the case-studies investigated reported in Tab. 6 together with the values of the norm of the *LHS* calculated via inverse kinematic approach. It is worth noting that, as for the case of 3D end-effector, when the system is minimally constrained or overconstrained ($m \geq n$) the procedure developed in this work provides through the IK approach the exact positioning of

the end-effector although signalling slack cables configurations; in fact, both for points inside and outside the workspace, the values of $\|LHS\|$ is always very small, corresponding to an almost zero residual of the objective function used in the minimization procedure.

380 A further example of overconstrained CDPM is shown in Fig. 9 where the case of four cables having fixed end positioned at different heights is investigated. The workspace is depicted in Fig. 9a and Fig. 9b, while Figs. 9c and 9d show the CDPM configurations for the case of target point included into the workspace and outside it, respectively. The values of the effective aspect ratio and of the residual of $\|LHS\|$ are reported in Tab. 6 as Case 4.

Table 6: Effective aspect ratio Λ_i and residual values of the objective function $\|LHS\|$ for the lowest four case-studies investigated in the case of point mass CDPM.

Case 1	Fig. 6c, $\ LHS\ = 2.48 \times 10^{-8}$					Fig. 6d, $\ LHS\ = 5.18 \times 10^{-8}$				
i th cable	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Λ_i	1.001	1.001	0.999			1.005	0.999	1.387		
Case 2	Fig. 7c, $\ LHS\ = 6.42 \times 10^{-10}$					Fig. 7d, $\ LHS\ = 1.20 \times 10^{-9}$				
i th cable	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Λ_i	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0		8.123	0.999	1.0	9.226	
Case 3	Fig. 8c, $\ LHS\ = 6.35 \times 10^{-8}$					Fig. 8d, $\ LHS\ = 2.04 \times 10^{-10}$				
i th cable	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Λ_i	1.0	0.999	1.01	1.019	1.007	1.086	29.72	35.71	35.88	0.997
Case 4	Fig. 9c, $\ LHS\ = 1.36 \times 10^{-8}$					Fig. 9d, $\ LHS\ = 2.86 \times 10^{-9}$				
i th cable	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Λ_i	1.0	1.0	0.999	0.999		61.99	7707.4	0.859	0.988	

385 Finally, it is a further objective of this work to show the capability of the proposed modeling and solution strategy to perform a fast evaluation of the effective unstretched length of the cables of a given manipulator necessary to follow an exact pre-defined trajectory of the end-effector mass in the workspace. This ability is shown in Fig. 10 where, for an assigned helicoidal trajectory in the 3D space (black dots), are reported in blue the configurations reached via DK approach while in red are shown the configurations attained via
390 IK approach including additional target equations. In particular, Figs. 10a, 10b, 10c, and 10d show the configurations assumed by the CDPM to reach four different points belonging to the helicoidal curve. For all points belonging to the trajectory, the solution of the IK problem provided the positioning of the point mass end-effector with a residual of $\|LHS\|$ always lower than 10^{-8} .

395 From a computational point of view, the procedures developed in this work revealed to be relatively fast, needing a computational time necessary to perform the simulations, of few minutes for the 3D problem, and few seconds for the point mass problem.

Figure 6: Three cables equilibrium configurations ($\Lambda_i^0 = 1.01$) for the point mass end-effector. Top plots: workspace including all non-slack or moderately slack three cables configurations (blue points). Bottom plots: comparisons between cables configurations via DK (blue lines) and IK (red lines) approach, respectively. Dimensions are in [m].

Figure 7: Four cables equilibrium configurations ($\Lambda_i^0 = 1.01$) for the point mass end-effector. Top plots: workspace including all non-slack or moderately slack four cables configurations (blue points). Bottom plots: comparisons between cables configurations via DK (blue lines) and IK (red lines) approach, respectively. Dimensions are in [m].

Figure 8: Five cables equilibrium configurations ($\Lambda_i^0 = 1.01$) for the point mass end-effector. Top plots: workspace including all non-slack or moderately slack five cables configurations (blue points). Bottom plots: comparisons between cables configurations via DK (blue lines) and IK (red lines) approach, respectively. Dimensions are in [m].

Figure 9: Four cables configurations ($\Lambda_i^0 = 1.01$) for the point mass end-effector, cables fixed ends at different heights. Top plots: workspace including all non-slack or moderately slack four cables configurations (blue points). Bottom plots: comparisons between cables configurations via DK (blue lines) and IK (red lines) approach, respectively. Dimensions are in [m].

Figure 10: Six cables configurations ($\Lambda_2^0 = 1.01$), helicoidal trajectory: comparisons between cables configurations via DK (blue lines) and IK (red lines) approach, respectively. Dimensions are in [m].

7. Conclusions

The presented study clarified the role of cables in CDPM kinematics through their description by an elastic catenary. Due to the elasto-geometric modeling of the cables, the mechanical problem of finding compatible and equilibrium configurations of CDPMs under end-effector and cables weight was solved through a nonlinear algebraic problem obtained by manipulating compatibility, equilibrium and constitutive equations, so that both mechanical and kinematic variables, describing forces and displacements, respectively, were retained as main unknowns. In the case of a 3D rigid end-effector, the so-called direct kinematic problem, in which were assigned all the characteristics of the CDPM including the unstretched cables lengths, $3(m + 1)$ nonlinear algebraic equations are solved by expressing the compatibility and the equilibrium of the system through an equal number of unknowns, namely, $3m$ components of the constraints reactions and 3 finite rotations of the rigid body.

The proposed formulation of the DK problem was then used to solve the IK problem through a novel procedure where m further equations, here named the *target equations*, and m new variables, namely, the cables lengths corrections, were introduced and the solution of the enlarged IK problem was found via the minimization of the error between the target configuration and the one evaluated by the DK solution. This allowed to evaluate the difference in the cables lengths necessary to drive the end-effector to the assigned position and orientation in space.

The ability of the proposed methodology was then discussed by a number of examples by considering either 3D rigid body and point mass end-effectors, this latter case straightforwardly derived from the 3D end-effector model. In particular, in all case-studies investigated the use of the effective aspect ratio to discriminate taut, moderately slack and slack initial unstretched configurations of the cables, respectively, was adopted to classify the calculated solutions. This allowed to define a procedure to determine the workspace in which a given CDPM operated by assuring that one (or more) initially loose cable configuration is avoided. Finally, trajectory tracking was also achieved through the proposed 3D model paving the way for further developments for possible future applications in control operations.

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